

1 **Outlier detection and gap filling methodologies for low-cost air quality**
2 **measurements**

3 **Thor-Bjorn Ottosen, Prashant Kumar***

4 *Global Centre for Clean Air Research (GCARE), Department of Civil and Environmental*
5 *Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Surrey, Guildford*
6 *GU2 7XH, United Kingdom*

7 **Abstract**

8 Air pollution is a major environmental health problem around the world, which needs to be
9 monitored. In recent years, a new generation of low-cost air pollution sensors has emerged.
10 Poor or unknown data quality, resulting from the intrinsic properties of the sensor as well as
11 the lack of a consensus on data processing methodologies for these sensors, has, among other
12 factors, prevented widespread adoption of these sensors. To contribute to the creation of this
13 consensus, we reviewed the available methodologies for quality control, outlier detection and
14 gap filling and applied two outlier detection methodologies and five gap filling methodologies
15 to a case study (consisting of an 11-month long air quality data set from a low-cost sensor). We
16 showed that erroneous data can be detected in a fully automated way, that point and contextual
17 outlier detection methodologies can be applied to low-cost air pollution data and yield
18 meaningful results, and that linear interpolation has the best performance for gap filling for
19 low-cost air pollution sensors. In conclusion, data cleaning procedures are important, and the
20 presented methods can form part of a generalised data processing methodology for low-cost
21 air pollution sensors.

22 **Keywords:** Air Pollution; Quality control; Missing data; Imputing; AQMesh

* Corresponding author. Address as above. Tel.: +44 1483 682762; Fax: +44 1483 682135; E-mail addresses: P.Kumar@surrey.ac.uk, Prashant.Kumar@cantab.net

23 1. Introduction

24 Air pollution is among the leading mortality risk factors globally.¹ Many countries
25 around the world have set up national air quality monitoring networks to assess compliance
26 with limit values, monitor implementation of policies to reduce air pollution concentrations,
27 and understand spatio-temporal patterns. Examples include Denmark,² UK,³ Germany⁴ and
28 USA.⁵ In this type of monitoring networks, the air quality instruments are characterised by high
29 accuracy[‡] and associated high costs.

30 In recent years, a new generation of air quality sensors has emerged that is characterised by
31 lower accuracy but also substantially lower costs.⁶ This development has spurred a large
32 number of studies. One branch has focused on the performance of specific sensors, e.g.,
33 Feinberg *et al.*⁷, Singer and Delp⁸ and Spinelle *et al.*⁹, recently reviewed by Rai *et al.*¹⁰ Another
34 branch has focused on specific applications of low-cost sensors such as mobile applications
35 e.g. Apte *et al.*¹¹ and human exposure Steinle *et al.*,¹² recently reviewed by Morawska *et al.*¹³
36 A third branch of research has focused on the development of data processing algorithms for
37 specific sensors or specific locations e.g. Zimmermann *et al.*¹⁴ and Cross *et al.*, which has been
38 treated separately from sensor performance even though these two are tightly connected as
39 recently discussed by Hagler *et al.*¹⁵

40 Poor or unknown data quality delivered by many low-cost air pollution sensors is a major
41 hindrance for more widespread adoption^{10, 16}. A contributing factor to this problem is the lack
42 of a consensus on data processing methodologies for low-cost air pollution sensors, since most
43 previous studies on sensor performance have used the data directly from the sensor without
44 further data processing. To contribute to the creation of this consensus, we propose that a
45 generic data processing methodology could be broken down into the following steps, based on
46 the framework proposed by van Zoest *et al.*¹⁸: (i) quality control and outlier detection; (ii)
47 comparison with classical monitors; (iii) comparison of inter-sensor measurements; (iv) gap

48 filling; (v) drift detection; (vi) noise removal; (vii) trend analysis; and (viii) case-specific data
49 analysis. Some would argue for a different order of steps, and it is a future research challenge
50 to work out the exact order of operations. Using the above framework the majority of the
51 previous studies on data processing for low-cost sensors have focused on steps (ii) and (iii)¹²,
52 ¹⁹⁻²⁷, whereas the remaining steps have received less attention, steps that have been shown to
53 be of great importance in other branches of science²⁸. Automated methods for data cleaning is
54 likewise in short supply among regulatory air quality monitoring programmes. This has
55 however traditionally been less of a problem due to the availability of resources to allow
56 manual data cleaning.²⁹ The rapidly growing data amounts from low-cost sensors mean that
57 manual data cleaning is no longer feasible.³⁰ As a stepping-stone towards a more generally
58 applicable data processing methodology, the focus of the present article is on quality control
59 and outlier detection as well as gap filling of low-cost sensors data. We choose these steps since
60 the removal of low-quality data and outliers from a dataset leads to gaps that subsequently have
61 to be filled. A number of terms have been used to describe data deviating markedly from the
62 other data, such as “outlier detection, novelty detection, anomaly detection, noise detection,
63 deviation detection or exception mining”.³¹ In this article, the term *outlier detection* will be
64 used consistently throughout in line with the approach taken by Hodge and Austin.³¹

65 Both *gap filling* and *imputation* have been used to describe the process of replacing missing
66 data with substituted values. In the present article, the term *gap filling* will be used throughout.

67 The aim of our work here is to review the available methodologies, apply a selection of
68 commonly applied methods to a case study (consisting of an 11 months long time series of
69 primary data from a low-cost sensor), and discuss the applicability of each methodology.

70 Here, we use a long time series measurement where a low-cost sensor system has been mounted
71 on a bus stop, as a case study, to test the applicability of the given method. The rationale behind
72 the design and instrumentation used in the case study is detailed in Section 2. Section 3 describe

73 the outcome of the review and discuss the selected methodologies. The results are presented in
74 Section 4, followed by the conclusions and recommendations in Section 5.

75 **2. Measurements**

76 The measurements of this study consist of a time series measurement from 10 July 2017
77 to 26 June 2018 with a single AQMesh sensor (Environmental Instruments Ltd, UK,
78 www.aqmesh.com). The AQMesh sensor has been used in a range of previous studies, e.g. for
79 air quality at a railway station,³² for comparison with high-end sensors,^{21,33} for monitoring air
80 quality at kindergartens³⁴ and for development of calibration procedures³⁵. The sensor
81 measured the species NO, NO₂, SO₂, CO, and O₃ using electrochemical sensors at 15 minutes
82 temporal resolution. The sensor pod also measured temperature, relative humidity and
83 atmospheric pressure. A proprietary algorithm is applied to the measurements to correct for the
84 influence of temperature and relative humidity as well as for cross-interference.

85 The sensor pod was mounted on the stand of a bus stop in the University of Surrey (Guildford,
86 Surrey, UK) campus area, to increase the understanding of air pollution exposure at bus
87 stops.³⁶⁻³⁸ An aerial photo of the location is provided in the Supplementary Information (SI)
88 Figure S1. The height of the sensor pod was 2.7 m above the ground level. The bus stop is
89 being serviced by two bus lines. The bus stop is serviced six-times per hour in daytime for the
90 stand immediately next to the sensor, and twelve times per hour during daytime for the stand a
91 bit further away.

92 **3. Data processing methodology**

93 Outliers can be caused by a range of different processes such as sensor errors, data
94 logger errors, network connectivity errors, or simply exceptional situations in terms of air
95 pollution. In the present study, we divide the outlier detection process into two parts based on
96 the degree of outlierness and the characteristics of the measurement: The first part is termed
97 “quality control” (Section 3.1) and aims to remove data points with extreme values or groups

98 of data with extreme statistical properties. This type of outliers are usually most often caused
99 by technical errors in the sensor or in the data logging system, and this type of outlier is
100 therefore termed “error”. The second part is termed “outlier detection” (described in section
101 3.2) and aims to remove single data points that are significantly dissimilar to their neighbouring
102 points. This type of outlier is in this context termed “outlier”.

103 3.1 Quality control

104 The AQMesh sensor comes with a status tag for each species, which is used for quality
105 control in the present study. The status can take on six values being *Stabilizing*, *Rebasing*,
106 *Greater Than Upper Limit*, *Less Than Lower Limit*, *Valid* and N/A. No values are recorded
107 while the status tag is *Stabilizing*. Only measurements with the *Valid* status were retained. This
108 was done both on a species-by-species level and for all the species in one go.

109 A visual inspection of the data showed that some of the sensors reported erroneous
110 measurements despite having a *Valid* status. The erroneous measurements are seen as abrupt
111 changes in the mean and/or the variance of the time series and have to be removed as part of
112 the quality control. To detect these points, the Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) algorithm,³⁹
113 which is one of the commonly applied methods for change detection in time series,⁴⁰⁻⁴² was
114 used. SI Section S1 provides a short description of this algorithm. The measurements classified
115 as erroneous was assigned their own status tag called *Error*.

116 3.2 Outlier detection

117 3.2.1 Overview of detection techniques

118 An extensive review of the literature on outlier detection was presented in.⁴³ To limit
119 the scope of the present study, two commonly applied methods, representing different
120 approaches (point outlier detection and contextual outlier detection) for outlier detection, were
121 selected for implementation:

- 122 • *k*-Nearest Neighbour (*k*-NN) is one of the simplest outlier detection methodologies and
123 serves as an example of a point outlier detection method. A short description of the
124 technique is given in SI Section S2. The *k*-NN approach has been widely used (e.g. Byers
125 and Raftery⁴⁴ and Guttormsson *et al.*⁴⁵) and has the advantage that it utilizes the fact that
126 data are multivariate.
- 127 • Regression-based outlier detection is an example of a contextual outlier detection
128 method. This approach has the advantage to take the temporal aspect of the data into
129 account. A model which has been extensively used in regression-based techniques is
130 AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Lu *et al.*⁴⁶ and Bianco *et al.*⁴⁷,
131 which is also used in the present study. A short description of this technique is given in
132 SI Section S3.

133 A commonly applied technique for collective outlier detection is the HOT-SAX algorithm.⁴⁸
134 This approach was also tested in the present study, but not included due to substantially long
135 run-time

136 **3.2.2 *k*-NN methodology**

137 The *k*-NN method was implemented using the Euclidian distance measure for
138 simplicity as widely used. Since the interval of the mean and standard deviation of the different
139 species is smaller than a factor of ten, no normalization was applied to the data before the
140 distance was calculated. To avoid the challenge of selecting *k*, the average Euclidian distance
141 to the remaining points was used to assign the outlier score of the individual data point,
142 following the approach of Angiulli and Pizzuti⁴⁹. To distinguish between outliers and other
143 instrumental artifacts (e.g. long-term drift), the distance was only calculated to the points within
144 an interval of ± 3.5 days of the data point, such that a full week of data was used in the
145 calculation for each point. This assumption is fortified by the fact that regional scale air
146 pollution changes happen on a time scale of days to weeks. The outlier detection proceeded in
147 two steps:

- 148 1. To define the threshold between outliers and normal data points, a *k*-means clustering with
149 two clusters was performed on the distances.
- 150 2. The AQMesh sensor consists of one sensor for each species.²¹ This means that even though
151 a given measurement is classified as an outlier, one or more of the measurements might
152 still be useful. To distinguish between outlying species and non-outlying species the
153 contribution of each species to the total Euclidean distance was calculated, and a *k*-means
154 clustering with two clusters (outliers and non-outliers) was applied to the contributions for
155 each data point. Only measurements classified as outliers in the first step was subsequently
156 classified at the species level.

157 **3.2.3 ARIMA methodology**

158 To detect contextual outliers, an ARIMA model was fitted to the time series from each
159 species from the AQMesh sensor separately, as the sensor consists of individual sensors for
160 each species. The ARIMA model was fitted to the data through the approach of Hyndman and
161 Khandakar^{50, 51} implemented in the `auto.arima` function from the forecast package
162 (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/forecast/index.html>) in R⁵². The function was run with
163 the standard settings, as a range of alternative settings were tested with only negligible effect
164 on the model performance. This function handles missing data through the approach of Jones⁵³
165 using the Kalman filter for likelihood evaluation. The outlier score for each data point was
166 subsequently calculated as the absolute value of the residual between the model and the
167 measurements while the classification into outliers and non-outliers was calculated using the
168 *k*-means clustering with two clusters.

169 **3.3 Gap filling**

170 **3.3.1 Assessment methodology**

171 The analyses on gap filling methodologies were applied to the measurements after the
172 ARIMA method had been used to remove outliers. The ARIMA method was used to preserve
173 the maximum number of measurements for this step.

174 To validate the performance of the different gap-filling methods, cross-validation was applied
175 following similar approaches such as presented by Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴. The impact of a gap on
176 the air quality measurements depends on the length of the gap, the proportion of the total time
177 series missing and the location of the gap in the time series⁵⁴. Testing all combinations of gap
178 length, gap proportion and gap location would be infeasible due to the combinatorics of the
179 number of combinations. Moreover, most combinations with short gap length and low
180 proportions of gaps are trivially easy to fill. From an application point of view, these
181 combinations are neither very interesting since they have negligible influence on the resulting
182 distribution and thus make the gap-filling superfluous.

183 To be able to discern between the performance of the different gap-filling methods, a validation
184 dataset consisting of combinations of gap length (0-100 data points), gap proportion (5-50% of
185 time series) and gap location with large impacts on the resulting distributions were designed in
186 the following way:

- 187 • In the first step, all potential gap locations were found by looping through the time series.
188 For multivariate gap filling methods, only measurements where all four species had
189 measurements were included in this step.
- 190 • The probability of sampling each gap location was assigned to the mean of the relative
191 difference between the mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis of the original
192 dataset, and a dataset with a gap at this particular location. In this way, gap locations with
193 large effects on the resulting distribution had a disproportionately high probability of being
194 selected.
- 195 • For each combination of gap length and gap proportion, we selected 100 samples of the
196 possible locations in the time series.

197 The maximum gap length of 100 data points corresponds to 25 hours. It was selected as a
198 balance between having as large as possible a gap length and still having a substantial number
199 of gap locations to choose from.

200 Following the approach of Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴, a number of performance indicators were
201 calculated for each combination of gap length, gap percentage, gap location and gap filling
202 methodology. In order to assess the ability of the gap filling methodology to reconstruct the
203 original data distribution, the difference in mean, the standard deviation, the skewness and the
204 kurtosis between the filled and the original distribution was calculated. For comparison, the
205 same statistics was calculated for the distribution with gaps. Following Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴, the
206 correlation coefficient (R), the index of agreement (d), the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
207 and the Mean Average Error (MAE) between the filled time series and the original time series
208 was calculated to represent different aspects of performance statistics.

209 3.3.2 Overview of gap filling techniques

210 Simple univariate gap filling techniques such as linear interpolation and nearest
211 neighbour (not to be mistaken for the k-NN approach described in Section 3.2.2;⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶, as well
212 as more complicated gap filling methods such as neural networks,^{57,58} have been applied in air
213 pollution data without showing definitive advantages of one method over the other. To limit
214 the scope of the present study, three univariate and two multivariate gap filling methods were
215 selected for implementation:

- 216 • **Univariate linear interpolation.** This method is selected in the present study as one of
217 the simplest gap filling methods. In Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴, this method performed best among
218 the univariate methods.
- 219 • **Cubic spline fitting.** This method is included as an example of a slightly more
220 complicated method, including more data points on each side of the gap.

- 221 • **Univariate Neural Networks.** The most complicated gap filling method is Neural
222 Networks (NN). In this case, a feed-forward neural networks with a single hidden layer
223 and lagged inputs is implemented in the `nnetar` function in the forecast package in R
224 ^{50,51}. Neural network models are slightly more complex models and a description of the
225 principles behind the `nnetar` function can be found in section 11.3 of Hyndman and
226 Athanasopoulos⁵⁹.
- 227 • **Multivariate linear regression.** For multivariate gap filling, multivariate linear
228 regression was selected, as this is one of the simplest multivariate approaches. This was
229 implemented such that the missing species was fitted as a linear function of the
230 remaining four species. A short description of this technique is given in SI Section S4.
- 231 • **Multivariate Neural Networks.** As an example of a more complicated multivariate
232 approach, the `nnetar` function from the forecast package in R ^{50,51} was used again,
233 but this time with the remaining species as input.

234 **4. Results and discussion**

235 **4.1 Quality control**

236 Table 1 shows the summary of the results related to the quality control procedure applied in
237 our work while Figure 1 shows the same results as a time series plot. It is evident from Table
238 1 and Figure 1 that *Missing data*, *Stabilizing* and *Rebasing* are the same for all five sensors,
239 except for CO, which is not rebasing after stabilizing around 1 November 2017. Neither of
240 these effects shows a significant influence on the gaps created due to quality control, owing to
241 their low proportions of the total data series. The *Less Than Lower Limit* is causing more than
242 10% gaps for both NO and CO and smaller gaps for SO₂ and O₃. Moreover, the gaps are only
243 partially overlapping from species to species, thus leading to a larger total data loss in the total
244 column. CO has a large section at the beginning of the time series influenced by the *Less Than*
245 *Lower Limit* quality tag leading to significant gaps in the time series. Part of this can be sensor
246 malfunctioning. The *Greater Than Upper Limit* tag also has some influence on the data loss

247 during quality control mainly for NO₂. For the gap around 1 February 2018, the quality problem
248 influences all five sensors. Some of these data points had a *Valid* tag from the sensor and was
249 removed by the PELT quality control procedure as seen in Figure 1. For SO₂, the variance
250 increased by approximately a factor of 100 at the end of the time series as seen in Figure 1,
251 which explains why the quality control procedure classified these data as erroneous. As seen
252 from the *Average* column in Table 1, the total gap percentage caused by quality control is more
253 than 10%, which will have a significant influence on any subsequent data analysis.

254

255 **Table 1.** Number of measurements and percentage of each quality tag for each species from the AQMesh sensor. The average is the average percentage
 256 of low-quality data across species for the specific quality tag. The total column represents an error in one of the species for row 2-7 and a valid data point
 257 for all five species for row 8. # represents the number of measurements.

	NO		NO ₂		SO ₂		CO		O ₃		Average	Total	
Unit:	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	%	#	%
1 Data before quality control	33685	100.0	33685	100.0	33685	100.0	33685	100.0	33685	100.0	100.0	33685	100.0
2 Missing data	12	0.0	12	0.0	12	0.0	0	0.0	12	0.0	0.0	12	0.0
3 Stabilizing	347	1.0	347	1.0	347	1.0	347	1.0	347	1.0	1.0	347	1.0
4 Rebasing	384	1.1	384	1.1	384	1.1	192	0.6	384	1.1	1.0	384	1.1
5 Less Than Lower Limit	3953	11.7	0	0.0	1162	3.4	4832	14.3	1147	3.4	6.6	7448	22.1
6 Greater than Upper Limit	0	0.0	1330	3.9	0	0.0	3	0.0	175	0.5	0.9	1330	3.9
7 Error	248	0.7	0	0.0	4312	12.8	4	0.0	9	0.0	2.7	4573	13.6
8 Data after quality control	28741	85.3	31612	93.8	27468	81.5	28307	84.0	31611	93.8	87.7	21104	62.7

258

259

260 **Figure 1.** Quality control of the different species. Since many of the low-quality data are orders
 261 of magnitude smaller or larger than the valid data, the low-quality data are plotted at the

262 maximum value of the valid data regardless of the actual value for ease of visualization. Note
263 that the y-axis is logarithmic. Negative values that are not labelled as “valid” in the intrinsic
264 QC procedure have been marked with a red bar in the top of the figure.

265 4.2 Outlier detection

266 Figure 2 shows the results of the k -NN outlier detection methodology for the different
267 species. The gaps in the time series are resulting from data being removed in the quality control
268 step. Since k -NN is a multivariate method, only data where all five species have passed the
269 quality control have been retained. It can be seen from this figure that, according to this
270 methodology, there are more outliers in the dataset for NO and CO compared to the other
271 species – a fact also emphasised in Table 2. Both of these species are dominating in traffic
272 exhaust and, given that the measurements were conducted on a bus stop, a certain amount of
273 spikes are to be expected in these time series. Some of the outliers present in Figure 2 for these
274 species might thus be an overestimation. The higher concentrations for these species will also
275 influence this result, as no normalization has been applied to the data before outlier detection.
276 For CO, the method has detected the level shift shortly before September 2017, which is a
277 misclassification, since these data points are not outliers, but rather an example of abrupt drift⁶⁰
278 – an instrumental artefact that future research should aim to remove. For O₃, the method has
279 failed to identify a large number of very low values as outliers.

280 Figure 3 shows the results of the ARIMA outlier detection methodology. It is evident that this
281 method classifies significantly more data points as outliers compared to the k -NN method, a
282 fact also underlined by Table 2. Since this method is univariate many more data points can be
283 included from the quality control step, thus leading to more outliers classified in absolute terms.
284 Like the k -NN method, the classified outliers are dominated by the high concentrations for NO,
285 NO₂, SO₂ and CO. However, this method also has a large number of outliers with lower

286 concentrations a phenomenon almost absent for the k -NN method. For O₃, it is evident that the
287 low concentration outliers have been correctly identified.

288 Table 2 highlights that the ARIMA method classifies more outliers than the k -NN method both
289 on a species by species level and for the whole sensor. The exception is CO, where the two
290 methods have roughly the same number of outliers. From the calculated agreement between
291 the two methods (shown in Table 2), it can be seen that there is a large degree of agreement in
292 the outliers for NO and NO₂, but a lower degree of agreement for the remaining species. This
293 can, for instance, be seen for CO, where the k -NN method tends to find outliers grouped at a
294 specific location in the data, whereas the ARIMA method distributes the outliers more
295 homogeneously. It is seen from Table 2, that if working with individual species, more data will
296 be retained by the ARIMA method, since fewer data will be lost in the quality control step.
297 However, if working with all five species, more data will be retained by the k -NN method,
298 since fewer data are removed as outliers. Comparison of Table 1 and Table 2 also shows that
299 the quality control procedure (Section 3.1) applied in the present study, as a rule, removes a
300 larger proportion of data compared to outlier detection.

301 For comparison, van Zoest *et al.*¹⁸ found an outlier percentage of between 0% and 0.7% for a
302 large number of low-cost sensors and conventional air pollution monitors. Our numbers are
303 higher since our data consist of 15 minutes averages as opposed to hourly averages used in van
304 Zoest *et al.*¹⁸. Moreover, van Zoest *et al.*¹⁸ used a distribution-based approach to outlier
305 detection, where the number of outliers is approximately determined in advance. This is
306 contrary to our approach, where the number of outliers is determined from the data (Table 2).

307

308 **Figure 2.** Time series plot of the five species measured by the AQMesh sensor classified using
 309 the *k*-NN method. The data classified as outliers are marked with red. Data classified as

310 “Stabilizing”, “Rebasing”, “Less Than Lower Limit”, Greater Than Upper Limit” or “Error”
311 have been removed by the QC procedure (section 3.1). Note that the y-axes are different.
312 Negative values for O3 have not been removed manually to assess the ability of the algorithm
313 to automatically remove these.

315 **Figure 3.** Time series plot of the five species measured by the AQMesh sensor classified using
 316 the ARIMA method. The data classified as outliers are marked with red. Data classified as
 317 “Stabilizing”, “Rebasing”, “Less Than Lower Limit”, “Greater Than Upper Limit” or “Error”
 318 have been removed by the QC procedure (section 3.1). Note that the y-axes are different.
 319 Negative values for O₃ have not been removed manually to assess the ability of the algorithm
 320 to automatically remove these.

321 **Table 2.** Number of and percentage of outliers for the individual species measured from the
 322 AQMesh instrument for each methodology. All percentages except in the “Agreement” row
 323 are calculated in relation to the number of measurements before quality control. The average
 324 percentage is the average across species, and the total number of and percentage of outliers is
 325 the number and percentage of data points where one or more species is classified as an outlier.
 326 The “Agreement” row represents the number and percentage of overlap in the classified outliers
 327 between the two methods. The percentage of this row is calculated in relation to the minimum
 328 number of outliers from the two methods as this is the maximum overlap between the two
 329 methods.

	NO		NO ₂		SO ₂		CO		O ₃		Average	Total	
Unit	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	%	#	%
<i>k</i> -NN	506	1.5	62	0.2	0	0.0	1293	3.8	61	0.2	1.1	1540	4.6
ARIMA	910	2.7	2184	6.4	772	2.3	1024	3.0	2908	8.6	4.6	4472	13.3
Agreement	329	65.0	54	87.1	0	0.0	363	35.4	17	27.9	43.1		
Remaining after <i>k</i> -NN	20598	61.1	21042	62.5	21104	62.7	19811	58.8	21043	62.5	61.5	19564	58.1
Remaining after ARIMA	27831	82.6	29428	87.4	26696	79.3	27283	81.0	28703	85.2	83.1	16632	49.4

331 **Table 3** Summary statistics for the univariate gap filling methods. Δ is the difference between
 332 the parameter for the distribution without gaps and the parameter for the filled distribution. The
 333 following statistics are presented: (μ) mean, (σ) standard deviation, (γ) skewness, (κ) kurtosis,
 334 (R) correlation, (d) index of agreement, (RMSE) Root Mean Square Error, (MAE) Mean
 335 Average Error.

	$\Delta\mu$	$\Delta\sigma$	$\Delta\gamma$	$\Delta\kappa$	R	d	RMSE	MAE
NO								
No gap filling	2.54	1.99	0.06	0.50				
Linear interpolation	0.74	0.69	0.05	0.54	0.69	0.82	22.89	15.59
Spline interpolation	3.44	75.41	2.45	25.48	0.17	0.25	211.63	121.35
Neural Networks	3.75	1.64	0.31	1.43	0.41	0.60	36.48	27.82
NO₂								
No gap filling	1.87	0.68	0.06	0.20				
Linear interpolation	0.37	0.27	0.02	0.13	0.75	0.86	10.98	7.87
Spline interpolation	0.77	13.51	0.97	10.55	0.32	0.42	59.83	39.26
Neural Networks	2.46	0.99	0.18	0.66	0.40	0.59	22.94	17.80
SO₂								
No gap filling	0.30	0.15	0.10	0.61				
Linear interpolation	0.08	0.05	0.04	0.19	0.91	0.95	2.34	1.57
Spline interpolation	0.33	6.00	1.39	16.04	0.35	0.43	18.68	10.98
Neural Networks	0.57	0.32	0.21	0.87	0.65	0.75	4.98	3.79
CO								
No gap filling	3.96	3.41	0.11	1.58				
Linear interpolation	0.53	0.75	0.02	0.20	0.94	0.97	32.51	22.13
Spline interpolation	2.99	40.28	0.77	5.88	0.52	0.62	176.72	111.35
Neural Networks	6.51	7.42	0.22	1.64	0.61	0.73	80.29	56.89
O₃								
No gap filling	0.39	0.95	0.14	0.40				
Linear interpolation	0.13	0.28	0.01	0.14	0.92	0.96	9.07	6.50
Spline interpolation	0.43	4.85	0.25	1.63	0.60	0.70	36.27	26.03
Neural Networks	1.25	1.14	0.15	0.62	0.75	0.81	17.74	12.82

336

337

338 **Figure 4.** Performance statistics for the three univariate gap filling methods as a function of

339 gap length in hours. Δ is the difference between the parameter for the distribution without gaps

340 and the parameter for the filled distribution. The following statistics are presents: (μ) mean, (σ)

341 standard deviation, (γ) skewness, (κ) kurtosis, (R) correlation, (d) index of agreement, (RMSE)

342 Root Mean Square Error, (MAE) Mean Average Error.

343

344 **Figure 5.** Performance statistics for the three univariate gap filling methods as a function of
 345 gap percentage. Δ is the difference between the parameter for the distribution without gaps and
 346 the parameter for the filled distribution. The following statistics are presents: (μ) mean, (σ)
 347 standard deviation, (γ) skewness, (κ) kurtosis, (R) correlation, (d) index of agreement, (RMSE)
 348 Root Mean Square Error, (MAE) Mean Average Error.

349 **4.3 Gap filling**

350 4.3.1 Univariate gap filling methods

351 Table 3 shows the performance statistics for each species for each univariate gap filling
352 method. The equivalent table for the multivariate methods is found in SI Table S1. It is evident
353 that linear interpolation has the best performance for all species for all performance statistics,
354 a result also found by Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴ The results also confirm that spline interpolation has
355 the worst performance in line with results presented by Junninen⁵⁴. Table 3 also shows that
356 linear interpolation works particularly well for SO₂, CO and O₃ with values >0.9 for correlation
357 and index of agreement. For SO₂, the good performance is confirmed by the RMSE and MAE
358 also being very low, which relates to the generally lower values of this species. Comparing the
359 distribution related statistics between the distributions with and without filling, it can be seen
360 that in general linear interpolation reduces the difference in these statistics, whereas the two
361 other methods increase the difference for these statistics. None of the multivariate methods
362 have better performance than linear interpolation, but linear regression and multivariate neural
363 networks perform better than spline interpolation and univariate neural networks.

364 Figure 4 shows the performance statistics for the three univariate methods as a function of gap
365 length. The equivalent figure for the multivariate methods can be found in SI Figure S2 It is
366 evident, that especially the performance of the spline method quickly declines as a function of
367 gap length. From the four last figures, it is evident that the performance of linear interpolation
368 is decreasing in terms of R and d and smaller increases are seen in RMSE and MAE as a
369 function of gap length, whereas the NN method has almost unchanged performance, however
370 worse than linear interpolation. The opposite is true for the multivariate case, where increasing
371 performance is shown for linear regression and for the four distribution-based statistics for
372 multivariate neural networks. The reason is that as the gap length increases, the measurements
373 that have to be filled will gradually approach the general trend of the whole data series. This
374 increases the performance of the two regression-based gap filling methods. It is thus plausible,
375 that for gaps longer than 25 hours linear regression and/or neural networks would actually

376 outperform linear interpolation – a result found in Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴. Given that the present study
377 was conducted on data with substantial amounts of data removed by quality control and outlier
378 detection, this analysis has not been possible in the present study.

379 Figure 5 shows the effect of gap percentage on the three univariate gap filling methods. The
380 equivalent table for the multivariate methods can be found in SI Figure S3. It is evident that
381 especially the performance of the NN method declines as a function of gap percentage. The
382 same is found for the multivariate case, where whereas especially neural networks, but also to
383 some extent linear regression has decreasing performance as a function of gap percentage. This
384 relates to that the two methods relies on fits to the data, and the fewer data to fit to, the worse
385 the performance. This is natural given that NN is a kind of non-linear regression, which means
386 that as less information becomes available for the fit, the worse the performance of the
387 interpolation. Also, the spline method shows decreasing performance with increasing gap
388 percentage, whereas the linear interpolation is almost independent of gap percentage. For the
389 spline method, this is probably related to an increasing number of gaps with increasing gap
390 percentage leads to deteriorated performance, since this method is only dependent on the data
391 in the vicinity of the gap.

392

393 Comparing our results to the results from Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴, there is agreement that the best
394 performance is achieved with linear interpolation for short gaps. For longer gap lengths than
395 included in the present study, Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴ finds a better performance for more complicated
396 gap filling methods. The fact that Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴ is using hourly values where as we are using
397 a temporal resolution of 15 minutes, will, all other things being equal, mean a better
398 performance for linear interpolation compared to the other methods. Junninen *et al.*⁵⁴ has
399 however only studied a gap percentage of 10 and 25, and as shown in Figure 5 and SI Figure

400 S3, the performance of the regression based methods deteriorated as a function of gap
401 percentage.

402 **5. Conclusion**

403 This study is a first step towards a consensus on data processing methodologies for low-
404 cost air pollution sensors in a number of ways. We have shown that how the PELT algorithm
405 could be used to remove erroneous data. The AQMesh dataset used here contained a substantial
406 number of outliers, but differences from species to species were large. Two outlier detection
407 methodologies were applied to a low-cost air pollution sensor data set and their strengths and
408 weaknesses were discussed. *k*-NN retains more data if all five species have to be included in
409 the analysis, whereas ARIMA retains more data on a species by species level. Three univariate
410 and two multivariate gap filling techniques were applied. Linear interpolation showed the best
411 performance. The performance of the different gap-filling methodologies was found to depend
412 strongly on gap length and gap percentage.

413 Data processing methodologies for low-cost air pollution sensors is an emerging data science
414 topic. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this study presents the first example where
415 automatic quality control, as well as gap filling, has been applied, and one of the first to study
416 outlier detection methodologies for this type of data. We expect that more sophisticated
417 techniques for both quality control, outlier detection and gap filling for low-cost air pollution
418 sensors will be developed in the coming years. This is expected to be followed by developments
419 in, for example, sensor comparisons, drift detection, noise removal and trend analysis.

420 One remaining question is how many of the data classified as outliers in the present study result
421 from technical errors and how many result from genuine measurements performed under rare
422 circumstances. This could be studied through a co-location campaign with a low-cost sensor
423 and one or more high-end instruments. This would also allow the application of supervised
424 outlier detection methodologies, which might achieve higher accuracy, as well as shed light on

425 the properties of the different outlier detection methodologies (e.g. close vs spread outliers).
426 Similar detailed analyses could be applied to the gap filling techniques. Another open question
427 is which method should be applied to fill the long gaps created by the quality control procedure
428 of the present study. This would require a more complete or a longer time series to address this
429 question. Lastly, a remaining question is how to handle spatial outliers in low-cost air pollution
430 data. The large gradients in the urban air quality concentrations means that traditionally it has
431 been a challenge to detect spatial outliers. The availability of networks of low-cost air pollution
432 sensors may be a future possibility to circumvent this problem.

433 **Conflicts of interest**

434 There are no conflicts to declare.

435 **Acknowledgements**

436 This work is carried out as a part of the iSCAPE (Improving Smart Control of Air Pollution in
437 Europe) project, which is funded by the European Community's H2020 Programme (H2020-
438 SC5-04-2015) under the Grant Agreement No. 689954. The authors acknowledge the
439 University of Surrey HPC resources, i.e. the Eureka cluster, made available for conducting the
440 research reported in this paper. We thank KV Abhijith for his help in AQMesh data collection
441 and Lance Wild from University of Surrey's Estate and Facilities department for help with
442 installation and maintenance of the AQMesh sensor.

443 **Notes and References**

444 †In the present article, the term *data quality* is used in line with the definition given in European
445 Commission⁶¹, meaning the *uncertainty*, *minimum data capture* and *minimum time coverage* of
446 a given set of measurements. The term *uncertainty* is then defined according to Joint
447 Committee for Guides in Metrology¹⁷ as *the non-negative parameter characterizing the*
448 *dispersion of the quantity values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information*

449 *used.* Contrary to this, the *measurement error* is defined as the *measured quantity value minus*
450 *a reference quantity value.*

- 451 1. A. J. Cohen, M. Brauer and R. Burnett, Estimates and 25-year trends of the global burden of
452 disease attributable to ambient air pollution: an analysis of data from the Global Burden of
453 Diseases Study 2015 (vol 389, pg 1907, 2017), *Lancet*, 2018, **391**, 1576-1576.
- 454 2. T. Ellermann, J. Nygaard, J. K. Nøjgaard, C. Nordstrøm, J. Brandt, J. Christensen, M. Ketzel, A.
455 Massling, R. Bossi and S. S. Jensen, *The Danish Air Quality Monitoring Programme. Annual*
456 *Summary for 2017*, Report 281, 2018.
- 457 3. DEFRA, *Air Pollution in the UK 2016*, Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs,, 2017.
- 458 4. A. Minkos, U. Dauert, S. Feigenspan, S. Kessinger, S. Nordmann and T. Himpel, *Air Quality*
459 *2017*, German Environment Agency, 2018.
- 460 5. EPA, *Our Nation's Air - Status and Trends Through 2010*, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
461 Office of Air Quality Planning and Standards, 2012.
- 462 6. P. Kumar, L. Morawska, C. Martani, G. Biskos, M. Neophytou, S. Di Sabatino, M. Bell, L. Norford
463 and R. Britter, The rise of low-cost sensing for managing air pollution in cities, *Environment*
464 *International*, 2015, **75**, 199-205.
- 465 7. S. Feinberg, R. Williams, G. S. W. Hagler, J. Rickard, R. Brown, D. Garver, G. Harshfield, P.
466 Stauffer, E. Mattson, R. Judge and S. Garvey, Long-term evaluation of air sensor technology
467 under ambient conditions in Denver, Colorado, *Atmos. Meas. Tech. Discuss.*, 2018, **2018**, 1-
468 18.
- 469 8. B. C. Singer and W. W. Delp, Response of consumer and research grade indoor air quality
470 monitors to residential sources of fine particles, *Indoor Air*, 2018, **28**, 624-639.
- 471 9. L. Spinelle, M. Gerboles and M. Aleixandre, Performance Evaluation of Amperometric Sensors
472 for the Monitoring of O₃ and NO₂ in Ambient Air at ppb Level, *Procedia Engineering*, 2015,
473 **120**, 480-483.

- 474 10. A. C. Rai, P. Kumar, F. Pilla, A. N. Skouloudis, S. Di Sabatino, C. Ratti, A. Yasar and D. Rickerby,
475 End-user perspective of low-cost sensors for outdoor air pollution monitoring, *Sci. Total*
476 *Environ.*, 2017, **607-608**, 691-705.
- 477 11. J. S. Apte, K. P. Messier, S. Gani, M. Brauer, T. W. Kirchstetter, M. M. Lunden, J. D. Marshall, C.
478 J. Portier, R. C. H. Vermeulen and S. P. Hamburg, High-Resolution Air Pollution Mapping with
479 Google Street View Cars: Exploiting Big Data, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2017, **51**, 6999-7008.
- 480 12. S. Steinle, S. Reis, C. E. Sabel, S. Semple, M. M. Twigg, C. F. Braban, S. R. Leeson, M. R. Heal, D.
481 Harrison, C. Lin and H. Wu, Personal exposure monitoring of PM_{2.5} in indoor and outdoor
482 microenvironments, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 2015, **508**, 383-394.
- 483 13. L. Morawska, P. K. Thai, X. Liu, A. Asumadu-Sakyi, G. Ayoko, A. Bartonova, A. Bedini, F. Chai,
484 B. Christensen, M. Dunbabin, J. Gao, G. S. W. Hagler, R. Jayaratne, P. Kumar, A. K. H. Lau, P. K.
485 K. Louie, M. Mazaheri, Z. Ning, N. Motta, B. Mullins, M. M. Rahman, Z. Ristovski, M. Shafiei, D.
486 Tjondronegoro, D. Westerdahl and R. Williams, Applications of low-cost sensing technologies
487 for air quality monitoring and exposure assessment: How far have they gone?, *Environ. Int.*,
488 2018, **116**, 286-299.
- 489 14. N. Zimmerman, A. A. Presto, S. P. N. Kumar, J. Gu, A. Haurlyliuk, E. S. Robinson, A. L. Robinson
490 and R. Subramanian, A machine learning calibration model using random forests to improve
491 sensor performance for lower-cost air quality monitoring, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2018, **11**, 291-
492 313.
- 493 15. G. S. W. Hagler, R. Williams, V. Papapostolou and A. Polidori, Air Quality Sensors and Data
494 Adjustment Algorithms: When Is It No Longer a Measurement?, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2018,
495 **52**, 5530-5531.
- 496 16. E. G. Snyder, T. H. Watkins, P. A. Solomon, E. D. Thoma, R. W. Williams, G. S. W. Hagler, D.
497 Shelow, D. A. Hindin, V. J. Kilaru and P. W. Preuss, The Changing Paradigm of Air Pollution
498 Monitoring, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2013, **47**, 11369-11377.
- 499 17. Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, International vocabulary of metrology – Basic and
500 general concepts and associated terms (VIM).*Journal*, 2012.

- 501 18. V. M. van Zoest, A. Stein and G. Hoek, Outlier Detection in Urban Air Quality Sensor Networks,
502 *Water, Air, Soil Pollut.*, 2018, **229**, 111.
- 503 19. D. H. Hagan, G. Isaacman-VanWertz, J. P. Franklin, L. M. M. Wallace, B. D. Kocar, C. L. Heald
504 and J. H. Kroll, Calibration and assessment of electrochemical air quality sensors by co-location
505 with regulatory-grade instruments, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2018, **11**, 315-328.
- 506 20. A. Cavaliere, F. Carotenuto, F. Di Gennaro, B. Gioli, G. Gualtieri, F. Martelli, A. Matese, P.
507 Toscano, C. Vagnoli and A. Zaldei, Development of Low-Cost Air Quality Stations for Next
508 Generation Monitoring Networks: Calibration and Validation of PM(2.5) and PM(10) Sensors,
509 *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, 2018, **18**, 2843.
- 510 21. N. Castell, F. R. Dauge, P. Schneider, M. Vogt, U. Lerner, B. Fishbain, D. Broday and A.
511 Bartonova, Can commercial low-cost sensor platforms contribute to air quality monitoring and
512 exposure estimates?, *Environ. Int.*, 2017, **99**, 293-302.
- 513 22. M. Gao, J. Cao and E. Seto, A distributed network of low-cost continuous reading sensors to
514 measure spatiotemporal variations of PM2.5 in Xi'an, China, *Environ. Pollut.*, 2015, **199**, 56-
515 65.
- 516 23. D. M. Holstius, A. Pillarisetti, K. R. Smith and E. Seto, Field calibrations of a low-cost aerosol
517 sensor at a regulatory monitoring site in California, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2014, **7**, 1121-1131.
- 518 24. A. S. Ali, Z. Zanzinger, D. Debose and B. Stephens, Open Source Building Science Sensors
519 (OSBSS): A low-cost Arduino-based platform for long-term indoor environmental data
520 collection, *Build. Environ.*, 2016, **100**, 114-126.
- 521 25. E. Austin, I. Novosselov, E. Seto and M. G. Yost, Laboratory Evaluation of the Shinyei PPD42NS
522 Low-Cost Particulate Matter Sensor, *PLoS One*, 2015, **10**, e0137789.
- 523 26. K. E. Kelly, J. Whitaker, A. Petty, C. Widmer, A. Dybwad, D. Sleeth, R. Martin and A. Butterfield,
524 Ambient and laboratory evaluation of a low-cost particulate matter sensor, *Environ. Pollut.*,
525 2017, **221**, 491-500.
- 526 27. E. S. Cross, L. R. Williams, D. K. Lewis, G. R. Magoon, T. B. Onasch, M. L. Kaminsky, D. R.
527 Worsnop and J. T. Jayne, Use of electrochemical sensors for measurement of air pollution:

- 528 correcting interference response and validating measurements, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2017, **10**,
529 3575-3588.
- 530 28. J. L. Campbell, L. E. Rustad, J. H. Porter, J. R. Taylor, E. W. Dereszynski, J. B. Shanley, C. Gries,
531 D. L. Henshaw, M. E. Martin, W. M. Sheldon and E. R. Boose, Quantity is Nothing without
532 Quality: Automated QA/QC for Streaming Environmental Sensor Data, *Bioscience*, 2013, **63**,
533 574-585.
- 534 29. T. B. Ottosen, M. Ketznel, H. Skov, O. Hertel, J. Brandt and K. E. Kakosimos, A parameter
535 estimation and identifiability analysis methodology applied to a street canyon air pollution
536 model, *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 2016, **84**.
- 537 30. M. Alavi-Shoshtari, J. A. Salmond, C. D. Giurcăneanu, G. Miskell, L. Weissert and D. E. Williams,
538 Automated data scanning for dense networks of low-cost air quality instruments: Detection
539 and differentiation of instrumental error and local to regional scale environmental
540 abnormalities, *Environ. Model. Software*, 2018, **101**, 34-50.
- 541 31. V. J. Hodge and J. Austin, A Survey of Outlier Detection Methodologies, *Artificial Intelligence
542 Review*, 2004, **22**, 85-126.
- 543 32. A. Hickman, C. Baker, X. Cai, J. Delgado-Saborit and J. Thornes, Evaluation of air quality at the
544 Birmingham New Street Railway Station, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Pt. F: J. Rail Rapid Transit*, 2018,
545 **232**, 1864-1878.
- 546 33. W. Jiao, G. Hagler, R. Williams, R. Sharpe, R. Brown, D. Garver, R. Judge, M. Caudill, J. Rickard,
547 M. Davis, L. Weinstock, S. Zimmer-Dauphinee and K. Buckley, Community Air Sensor Network
548 (CAIRSENSE) project: evaluation of low-cost sensor performance in a suburban environment
549 in the southeastern United States, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2016, **9**, 5281-5292.
- 550 34. N. Castell, P. Schneider, S. Grossberndt, M. F. Fredriksen, G. Sousa-Santos, M. Vogt and A.
551 Bartonova, Localized real-time information on outdoor air quality at kindergartens in Oslo,
552 Norway using low-cost sensor nodes, *Environ. Res.*, 2018, **165**, 410-419.
- 553 35. J. M. Cordero, R. Borge and A. Narros, Using statistical methods to carry out in field
554 calibrations of low cost air quality sensors, *Sensors Actuators B: Chem.*, 2018, **267**, 245-254.

- 555 36. D. B. Hess, P. D. Ray, A. E. Stinson and J. Park, Determinants of exposure to fine particulate
556 matter (PM_{2.5}) for waiting passengers at bus stops, *Atmos. Environ.*, 2010, **44**, 5174-5182.
- 557 37. E. Velasco and S. H. Tan, Particles exposure while sitting at bus stops of hot and humid
558 Singapore, *Atmos. Environ.*, 2016, **142**, 251-263.
- 559 38. A. Moore, M. Figliozzi and C. Monsere, Air Quality at Bus Stops, *Transportation Research
560 Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, 2012, **2270**, 76-86.
- 561 39. R. Killick, P. Fearnhead and I. A. Eckley, Optimal Detection of Changepoints With a Linear
562 Computational Cost, *J. Amer. Statistical Assoc.*, 2012, **107**, 1590-1598.
- 563 40. H. Wang, R. Killick and X. Fu, Distributional change of monthly precipitation due to climate
564 change: comprehensive examination of dataset in southeastern United States, *HyPr*, 2014, **28**,
565 5212-5219.
- 566 41. M. Leiss, H. H. Nax and D. Sornette, Super-exponential growth expectations and the global
567 financial crisis, *J. Econ. Dynam. Control*, 2015, **55**, 1-13.
- 568 42. J. Y. Kim, G. Rastogi, Y. Do, D.-K. Kim, P. R. Muduli, R. N. Samal, A. K. Pattnaik and G.-J. Joo,
569 Trends in a satellite-derived vegetation index and environmental variables in a restored
570 brackish lagoon, *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 2015, **4**, 614-624.
- 571 43. V. Chandola, A. Banerjee and V. Kumar, Anomaly detection: A survey, *ACM Comput. Surv.*,
572 2009, **41**, 1-58.
- 573 44. S. Byers and A. E. Raftery, Nearest-Neighbor Clutter Removal for Estimating Features in Spatial
574 Point Processes, *J. Amer. Statistical Assoc.*, 1998, **93**, 577-584.
- 575 45. S. E. Guttormsson, R. J. Marks, M. A. El-Sharkawi and I. Kerszenbaum, Elliptical novelty
576 grouping for on-line short-turn detection of excited running rotors, *ITEnC*, 1999, **14**, 16-22.
- 577 46. J. Lu, L. Shi and F. Chen, Outlier Detection in Time Series Models Using Local Influence Method,
578 *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 2012, **41**, 2202-2220.
- 579 47. A. M. Bianco, M. G. Ben, E. J. Martínez and V. J. Yohai, Outlier Detection in Regression Models
580 with ARIMA Errors using Robust Estimates, *Journal of Forecasting*, 2001, **20**, 565.

- 581 48. E. Keogh, J. Lin and A. Fu, presented in part at the Proceedings of the Fifth IEEE International
582 Conference on Data Mining, 2005.
- 583 49. F. Angiulli and C. Pizzuti, in *Principles of Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery. PKDD 2002*,
584 eds. E. T, M. H. and T. H., Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2002, vol. vol 2431,
585 pp. 15-27.
- 586 50. R. J. Hyndman and Y. Khandakar, Automatic Time Series Forecasting: The forecast Package for
587 R, *Journal of Statistical Software*, 2008, **27**, 22.
- 588 51. R. Hyndman, G. Athanasopoulos, C. Bergmeir, G. Caceres, L. Chhay, M. O'Hara-Wild, F.
589 Petropoulos, S. Razbash, E. Wang and F. Yasmeeen, *forecast: Forecasting functions for time*
590 *series and linear models*, 2019.
- 591 52. R Development Core Team, R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. *Journal*,
592 2019.
- 593 53. R. H. Jones, Maximum Likelihood Fitting of ARMA Models to Time Series with Missing
594 Observations, *Technometrics*, 1980, **22**, 389-395.
- 595 54. H. Junninen, H. Niska, K. Tuppurainen, J. Ruuskanen and M. Kolehmainen, Methods for
596 imputation of missing values in air quality data sets, *Atmos. Environ.*, 2004, **38**, 2895-2907.
- 597 55. A. Plaia and A. L. Bondì, Single imputation method of missing values in environmental pollution
598 data sets, *Atmos. Environ.*, 2006, **40**, 7316-7330.
- 599 56. M. N. Norazian, Y. A. Shukri, R. N. Azam and A. M. M. Al Bakri, Estimation of missing values in
600 air pollution data using single imputation techniques, *Scienceasia*, 2008, **34**, 341-345.
- 601 57. Ü. A. Şahin, C. Bayat and O. N. Uçan, Application of cellular neural network (CNN) to the
602 prediction of missing air pollutant data, *AtmRe*, 2011, **101**, 314-326.
- 603 58. A. Arroyo, A. Herrero, V. Tricio, E. Corchado and M. Wozniak, Neural Models for Imputation
604 of Missing Ozone Data in Air-Quality Datasets, *Complexity*, 2018, DOI:
605 10.1155/2018/7238015.
- 606 59. R. J. Hyndman and G. Athanasopoulos, *Forecasting: principles and practice. Journal*, 2018.

- 607 60. L. L. Minku, A. P. White and X. Yao, The Impact of Diversity on Online Ensemble Learning in
608 the Presence of Concept Drift, *IEEE Trans. on Knowl. and Data Eng.*, 2010, **22**, 730-742.
- 609 61. European Commission, DIRECTIVE 2008/50/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE
610 COUNCIL of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe. *Journal*, 2008,
611 **2008/50/EC**.

Supplementary Information (SI)

for

**Outlier detection and gap filling methodologies for low-cost air quality
measurements**

Thor-Bjorn Ottosen, Prashant Kumar²

*Global Centre for Clean Air Research (GCARE), Department of Civil and Environmental
Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Surrey, Guildford
GU2 7XH, United Kingdom*

² Corresponding author. Address as above. Tel.: +44 1483 682762; Fax: +44 1483 682135; E-mail addresses: P.Kumar@surrey.ac.uk, Prashant.Kumar@cantab.net

Figure S1. Aerial photo of the bus stop, where the measurements have been made. The location of the AQMesh pod is marked with a red dot. Data source: Google Earth.

S1. Pruned Exact Linear Time algorithm

Given an ordered sequence of data (in this case air quality measurements) $y_{1:n} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$, the aim of the algorithm is to find the number of changepoints m with positions $\tau_{1:m} = (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_m)$. To this end, the following expression is minimised:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{m+1} [C(y_{(\tau_{i-1}+1):\tau_i})] + \beta f(m) \quad (1)$$

Where C is a cost function for segment i and $\beta f(m)$ is a penalty function to prevent overfitting. In the PELT algorithm twice the negative log likelihood is used as cost function¹ and the penalty function is set equal to the number of changepoints. Calculating this expression for all possible combinations would yield 2^{n-1} calculations². The PELT algorithm is a faster way to minimise equation 1, and the interested reader is referred to¹ for details.

S2. k -Nearest Neighbor outlier detection

In k-Nearest Neighbor outlier detection, “The anomaly score of a data instance is defined as its distance to its k^{th} nearest neighbor in a given data set”³. In the present study the Euclidian distance is used:

$$d(\vec{p}, \vec{q}) = \sqrt{(q_1 - p_1)^2 + (q_2 - p_2)^2 + \dots + (q_n - p_n)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where \vec{p} and \vec{q} are two air quality measurements with the species representing the components of the vectors.

S3. Regression based outlier detection

In the present implementation of regression based outlier detection, an Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model is fitted to the data. The equation for the ARIMA model is⁴:

$$\phi(B)(1 - B^d)y_t = c + \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where y_t is the time series of air quality measurements, B is the backshift operator, $\phi(z)$ and $\theta(z)$ are polynomials of order p and q respectively. The outlier score is subsequently defined as the residual between the fitted model and the measurements.

S4. Multivariate Linear regression

Given an air quality measurement with multiple species $\vec{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_n)$, where p_1 is missing, the multivariate linear regression fits a function for p_1 as a function of the remaining species:

$$p_1 = \alpha_1 p_2 + \alpha_2 p_3 + \dots + \alpha_{n-1} p_n + \beta \quad (4)$$

Where α and β are regression coefficients.

Table S1. Summary statistics for the multivariate gap filling methods. Δ is the difference between the parameter for the distribution without gaps and the parameter for the filled distribution. The following statistics are presented: (μ) mean, (σ) standard deviation, (γ) skewness, (κ) kurtosis, (R) correlation, (d) index of agreement, (RMSE) Root Mean Square Error, (MAE) Mean Average Error.

	$\Delta\mu$	$\Delta\sigma$	$\Delta\gamma$	$\Delta\kappa$	R	d	RMSE	MAE
NO								
No gap filling	1.35	1.48	0.08	0.63				
Linear interpolation	0.36	0.15	0.02	0.17	0.79	0.88	14.25	8.35
Linear regression	0.82	0.54	0.03	0.46	0.76	0.83	16.02	12.44
Neural Networks	1.57	0.73	0.15	0.96	0.72	0.80	22.13	15.80
NO₂								
No gap filling	0.96	0.53	0.05	0.19				
Linear interpolation	0.23	0.10	0.01	0.05	0.82	0.90	8.32	5.91
Linear regression	0.73	0.77	0.05	0.49	0.11	0.39	16.53	13.34
Neural Networks	1.02	0.30	0.09	0.30	0.22	0.55	21.71	16.37
SO₂								
No gap filling	0.12	0.10	0.04	0.48				
Linear interpolation	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.08	0.96	0.98	1.69	1.07
Linear regression	0.13	0.24	0.04	0.67	0.86	0.86	3.42	2.97
Neural Networks	0.22	0.13	0.04	0.39	0.87	0.89	2.98	1.90
CO								
No gap filling	3.26	1.86	0.08	0.92				
Linear interpolation	0.21	0.28	0.01	0.05	0.96	0.98	23.81	15.90
Linear regression	2.34	6.31	0.11	1.59	0.68	0.66	76.36	55.58
Neural Networks	2.10	2.94	0.08	0.74	0.81	0.85	53.95	38.04
O₃								
No gap filling	0.82	0.47	0.08	0.19				
Linear interpolation	0.13	0.11	0.01	0.05	0.94	0.97	7.17	5.18
Linear regression	0.51	0.79	0.04	0.42	0.78	0.84	15.67	12.47
Neural Networks	0.61	0.35	0.05	0.17	0.86	0.91	12.79	9.40

Figure S2. Performance statistics for the two multivariate gap filling methods and linear interpolation as a function of gap length in hours. Δ is the difference between the parameter for the distribution without gaps and the parameter for the filled distribution. The following statistics are presents: (μ) mean, (σ) standard deviation, (γ) skewness, (κ) kurtosis, (R) correlation, (d) index of agreement, (RMSE) Root Mean Square Error, (MAE) Mean Average Error.

Figure S3. Performance statistics for the two multivariate gap filling methods and linear interpolation as a function of gap percentage. Δ is the difference between the parameter for the distribution without gaps and the parameter for the filled distribution. The following statistics are presents: (μ) mean, (σ) standard deviation, (γ) skewness, (κ) kurtosis, (R) correlation, (d) index of agreement, (RMSE) Root Mean Square Error, (MAE) Mean Average Error.

References

1. R. Killick, P. Fearnhead and I. A. Eckley, Optimal Detection of Changepoints With a Linear Computational Cost, *J. Amer. Statistical Assoc.*, 2012, **107**, 1590-1598.
2. R. Killick and I. A. Eckley, changepoint: An R Package for Changepoint Analysis, *Journal of Statistical Software*, 2014, **58**, 19.

3. V. Chandola, A. Banerjee and V. Kumar, Anomaly detection: A survey, *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 2009, **41**, 1-58.
4. R. J. Hyndman and Y. Khandakar, Automatic Time Series Forecasting: The forecast Package for R, *Journal of Statistical Software*, 2008, **27**, 22.